

Resin treatment for reliable transverse shear strength assessment in aerospace structures

T.R.C. Chuaqui*, A. T. Rhead, R. Butler

*Corresponding author. Materials and Structures Research Centre, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bath, Bath, UK, T.R.C.Chuaqui@bath.ac.uk

Introduction

Transverse shear strength testing is part of the extensive certification process of large aerospace structures. However, performing these tests on small scale specimens with exposed free edges, which are often non-existent in the final large scale product, leads to significant under-predictions of the strength of large components. In this work, a resin treatment is applied on the edges of short beam specimens effectively suppressing free edge effects and producing less conservative strength predictions. The effects of the treatment are analysed in detail using experiments, computed-tomography (CT) and finite element analysis (FEA). Knock-down factors due to defects are usually assessed during the certification process, so two material systems are tested herein (one pristine and one degraded).

Specimen preparation and test methodology

Material	Stacking sequence	Short Beam Test ASTM D2344/D2344M-13
977-2/HTS40	[±45/0/90 ₂ /0/+45] _S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 Untreated • 7 Treated
M21/T800S (degraded)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 Untreated • 9 Treated

Experimental results

Material	Treatment	Isotropic strength [MPa] [1]	Anisotropic strength [MPa] [2]	% Increase
977-2/HTS40	None	71.5 (±3.9)	79.8 (±4.4)	+28
	Resin	91.4 (±2.8)	102.0 (±3.1)	
M21/T800S (degraded)	None	51.8 (±3.5)	-	+42
	Resin	73.5 (±4.2)	-	

FEA results – Analysis of stresses and onset of delamination before and after treatment

3D ABAQUS FEA Model
 - Both untreated and treated tests
 - High mesh refinement near edges

Conclusions

- Experimental and numerical results show significant strength improvements in transverse shear strength after application of the resin treatment by effectively reducing free edge effects.
- The treatment resulted in **28%** and **42%** increase in strength of pristine 977-2/HTS40 and degraded M21/T800S material systems, respectively.
- CT-scans show that the treatment prevents damage localisation at ply interfaces with very high near-edge interlaminar stresses, resulting in a more widespread damage pattern.
- Stress concentrations at the edge are not completely removed due to mismatching properties of the resin used for the treatment and the resin of the CFRP material.
- Treatment can be implemented in the certification process of aerospace structures to produce less conservative transverse shear strength predictions of large components.

References:

- [1] - American Society for Testing and Materials. ASTM D2344/D2344M-13. Standard Test Method for Short-Beam Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials and Their Laminates, 2013.
 [2] - B. A. Bednarczyk, J. Aboudi, P.W. Yarrington, C. S. Collier. Simplified Shear Solution for Determination of the Shear Stress Distribution in a Composite Panel from the Applied Shear Resultant. In: 49th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials, pages 1-25, Schaumburg, Illinois, 2008.